

Response of rice genotypes to dissolved oxygen during seedling establishment under lowland conditions

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Despite its high oxidation potential, calper coating cannot ensure stable seedling establishment under direct-seeded lowland culture (Hagiwara and Imura 1995). Varying responses of calper to soils in accumulating dissolved oxygen (DO) and to genotype may affect seedling establishment in the lowland environment. A study was conducted using two soils: soil (Inceptisols, pH 4.8) collected from an upland and calcarous soil (Entisols, pH 6.8) collected from Akita Prefecture, Japan. The organic C content of both soils was 4%. To manipulate DO, one or five coated or noncoated seeds of Haenuki or Sasanishiki (rice genotype) were sown in test tubes containing 5 g of soil flooded by 10 mL of water and allowed to grow for 7 d at 30 °C in the dark.

Irrespective of calper coating, Akita soil accumulated only a trace amount of DO. Accumulated DO in upland soil for one and five coated seeds was 10.6 and 20.0 mg L⁻¹, respectively, measured using the hand-held DO temperature system (YSI model 55). Seedling establishment was excellent for Haenuki in both Akita and upland soils (Fig. 1). Compared with Haenuki, seedling establishment in Sasanishiki was poorer in Akita soil. The upland soil showed a fair amount (4.3–4.4 mg L⁻¹) of accumulated DO in noncoated seeds. Under this condition, the establishment of Sasanishiki was excellent. With an increase in accumu-

lated DO, the establishment and subsequent growth of this genotype decreased exponentially (Figs. 1 and 2). Seedling establishment and first-leaf growth of Haenuki were not affected by DO accumulation. However, its subsequent growth followed a polynomial pattern (Fig. 2) as shown by plant height and root elongation.

Results suggest that Sasanishiki did not tolerate either anoxia (0–0.12 mg L⁻¹ of DO) or

accumulated DO equivalent to or more than the aerobic level under flooded conditions. Aerobic conditions can enhance oxygen uptake seven times faster than can anaerobic conditions (Biswas 1994). Therefore, under saturated levels, accumulated DO was supposed to be consumed as soon as possible. Hence, germinating seeds were forced to encounter anaerobic stress. Since the oxidizing effect of calper is short-lived (Hagiwara and Imura 1995),

Fig. 1. Effect of dissolved oxygen (DO), soil, and genotype on seedling establishment and 1st leaf length.

Fig. 2. Effect of dissolved oxygen (DO), soil, and genotype on plant height and root length.

anaerobic stress on the seed has an irreparable effect. Haenuki may have tolerance for anoxia to sustain the stress. In contrast, Sasanishiki could not overcome the stress most probably because of its inability to withstand anoxia. Thus, the efficiency of calper coating seems to depend on both soil and genotype.

Acknowledgment

The senior author is indebted to the Japanese Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) for providing the postdoctoral fellowship to perform this work.

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The International Rice Functional Genomics Working Group

To facilitate collaboration and transfer of new findings from genomic research to applications, IRRI organized the International Rice Functional Genomics Working Group. The Working Group has the following objectives:

- Build a research community with a shared vision on rice functional genomics
- Create a common resource platform to broaden access to new knowledge and tools in functional genomics

- Accelerate application of functional genomics to rice improvement
- The Working Group is intended to be broad-based collaborative network that will benefit participants by pooling expertise and resources. To date, several institutions have expressed interest to participate in this working group.

Through a series of meetings and consultations, three activities that are considered high priority by the rice research community were identified:

1. Create an information node to communicate information related to functional genomics
2. Promote the sharing of genetic stocks

3. Facilitate sharing of resources for microarray analysis
- A Web-based information node was established as an entry point for finding and sharing information and providing links to individual laboratories or organizations with interest in rice functional genomics. For more information about the site and the Working Group, go to: <http://www.cgiar.org/irri>

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